
Assessment of Vegetation Health Using NDVI Derived from Landsat Images: A Case Study of Satara District, Maharashtra

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Abstract:

This research paper examines the spatiotemporal dynamics of vegetation health in Satara district, Maharashtra, from 1994 to 2024, using NDVI analysis as a proxy for ecological conditions. The findings reveal significant temporal variations, with the proportion of dense and very dense vegetation increasing from 26.36% and 7.45% in 1994 to 36.10% and 11.88% in 2024, respectively. Sparse vegetation peaked at 44.29% in 2004 but declined to 5.27% by 2024, indicating substantial improvements in vegetation health. Spatial analysis highlights the western hilly regions as hotspots of dense vegetation, attributed to higher rainfall and forest cover, while the eastern plains consistently exhibit sparse vegetation due to arid conditions, urban expansion, and intensive agriculture. The central region displayed transitional patterns, with moderate vegetation aligning with irrigation networks and river courses. Temporal trends reveal periods of vegetation decline, notably between 1999 and 2004, associated with environmental stressors such as drought and deforestation, followed by recovery and growth in subsequent years due to favorable climatic conditions and ecological interventions. Climatic variability and anthropogenic factors, including deforestation and unsustainable land use, were key drivers of NDVI fluctuations. The increasing trend in vegetation density in later years underscores the positive impact of afforestation initiatives, water-efficient irrigation practices, and soil conservation measures. In order to maintain vegetative health and improve ecological resilience, the study highlights the necessity of coordinated land and water resource management techniques. These findings serve as a foundation for policymakers to prioritize sustainable practices that balance environmental conservation with socio-economic development in the region.

Keywords: NDVI, Vegetation, Remote Sensing, GIS.

Introduction:

Vegetation health is a vital indicator of ecological stability, serving as a reflection of both climatic variability and human-induced changes in land use. The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) is widely recognized as a reliable tool for assessing vegetation cover, density, and health across temporal and spatial scales. Satara district, located in the western state of Maharashtra, presents a diverse topography ranging from hilly regions in the west to arid plains in the east.

This heterogeneity, coupled with varying climatic conditions and intensive land-use practices, makes the district a compelling case for understanding vegetation dynamics over time.

This study investigates the spatiotemporal changes in vegetation health in Satara district from 1994 to 2024, using NDVI as a quantitative measure. The temporal analysis captures variations in vegetation cover and density over three decades, highlighting the interplay of climatic factors such as rainfall anomalies

and anthropogenic pressures like deforestation, urbanization, and agricultural expansion. The spatial analysis explores regional disparities in vegetation health, focusing on the contrasting patterns between the western hilly regions, central transitional zones, and eastern plains.

Vegetation health is a crucial indicator for assessing environmental conditions such as drought, land degradation, and land-use changes. The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI), which measures the difference between near-infrared and red reflectance, is widely used for monitoring vegetation health due to its sensitivity to vegetation cover. NDVI values range from -1 to +1, with higher values indicating dense, healthy vegetation (Tucker, 1979). It has proven to be an effective tool for detecting temporal and spatial variations in vegetation conditions, making it particularly useful for environmental monitoring and agricultural planning (Pettorelli et al., 2005). Milanović et al. (2019) applied Landsat-derived NDVI to assess vegetation cover changes in Central Serbia from 2006 to 2014, highlighting a decrease in vegetation and discrepancies with official forest statistics. The study demonstrated NDVI's effectiveness in detecting illegal logging and providing up-to-date data for forest management.

The findings of this study are intended to provide critical insights into the factors influencing vegetation health and offer evidence-based recommendations for sustainable land and resource management. By identifying trends and drivers of vegetation change, this research contributes to the broader discourse on ecological resilience, climate adaptation, and sustainable development in semi-arid regions.

Objective:

The primary objective of this research paper is to evaluate vegetation health in Satara District, Maharashtra, over a 30-year period (1994–2023), utilizing the Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) derived from Landsat images. The study also seeks to analyze spatial and temporal patterns in vegetation health and identify areas of ecological concern, contributing to informed land-use and environmental management.

Study Area:

Figure 1 Location map of Satara District (Maharashtra).

Satara district, located in the western part of Maharashtra, India (Figure 1), spans an area of approximately 10,480 square kilometers. Geographically, it lies between latitudes 17°N to 18°15'N and longitudes 73°30'E to 75°E. The district's administrative framework includes eleven talukas and four revenue divisions, covering a total of 1,721 revenue villages. Satara's topography is diverse, featuring the Sahyadri Hills, plateaus, and plains.

The district experiences a generally favorable climate with distinct seasonal variations. The winter season extends from December to mid-February, followed by the summer season. The southwest monsoon season occurs from June to September, while the post-monsoon season lasts from October to November. Average temperatures range between a minimum of 14.4°C and a maximum of 36.8°C. Rainfall distribution

varies significantly, from as low as 473 mm in the eastern parts to approximately 6,209 mm in the western hilly regions, including Mahabaleshwar and the Sahyadri range.

The eastern region of the district, comprising Khandala, Phaltan, Khatav, and Man talukas, as well as parts of Koregaon and Karad talukas, is classified as a "drought-prone area." This region frequently experiences drought conditions, with over 20 of years affected, emphasizing its vulnerability to water scarcity. Conversely, the western parts of the district receive significantly higher rainfall, supporting agriculture and vegetation. Satara's economy relies heavily on agriculture, making the monitoring of vegetation health essential for

sustainable development. The semi-arid climate, coupled with varied topography and rainfall patterns, highlights the district's dependency on efficient water resource management and agricultural planning.

Materials and Method:

Data Acquisition: This study employed Landsat 5, 7, and 8 satellite imagery acquired from the USGS Earth Explorer platform. Imagery was selected for post-monsoon (January Month), covering the period from 1994 to 2024 at five-year intervals. To ensure data quality, cloud-free images with less than 0 cloud cover were prioritized.

Table 1 Landsat Data Acquisition.

Sensor Name	Satellite Name	Implied Path	Implied Row	Data Acquisition Period
Landsat 5 TM	Landsat 5	146,147	47, 48	1994, 1999
Landsat 7 ETM+	Landsat 7	146,147	47, 48	2004, 2009
Landsat 8 OLI	Landsat 8	146,147	47, 48	2014, 2019
Landsat 9 OLI-2	Landsat 9	146,147	47, 48	2024

Preprocessing: Preprocessing of satellite images was conducted using ArcGIS 10.4 and QGIS software. The key steps included:

1. **Radiometric Calibration** – Adjusting digital values to accurate reflectance levels.
2. **Atmospheric Correction** – Minimizing distortions caused by atmospheric conditions.
3. **Geometric Correction** – Ensuring spatial accuracy by aligning images with the geographic coordinate system.

These preprocessing steps were essential to ensure reliable reflectance values and minimize errors from sensor anomalies.

NDVI Calculation: The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index (NDVI) was calculated using the formula:

$$NDVI = (NIR - R) / (NIR + R)$$

..... (Tucker, 1979)

Where: **NIR (Near-Infrared Band)** Reflectance in the near-infrared spectrum and **R (Red Band)** Reflectance in the red spectrum. The NDVI values were categorized as follows:

Table 2 NDVI Values and Vegetation Health Categories.

Sr. No.	Category	NDVI Range
1	Barren Land	< 0
2	Sparse Vegetation	0 – 0.2
3	Moderate Vegetation	0.2 – 0.4
4	Dense Vegetation	0.4 – 0.6
5	Very Dense Vegetation	> 0.6

Seasonal and annual NDVI maps were generated to visualize and analyze vegetation distribution patterns.

Temporal and Spatial Analysis: Temporal trends in NDVI were assessed using linear regression to evaluate changes in vegetation health over time. Spatial distribution patterns

were analyzed through GIS-based techniques to identify regions exhibiting significant vegetation gain or loss.

Results and Discussion:

Table 3 NDVI Values and Vegetation Health Categories Area Percentage.

Category	Barren Land	Sparse Vegetation	Moderate Vegetation	Dense Vegetation	Very Dense Vegetation	Total Area
NDVI Range	< 0	0 – 0.2	0.2 – 0.4	0.4 – 0.6	> 0.6	
1994	1.19	19.71	45.29	26.36	7.45	100.00
1999	1.16	17.01	43.95	27.93	9.91	100.00
2004	1.07	44.29	32.18	14.98	7.46	100.00
2009	1.06	42.01	21.96	28.34	6.63	100.00
2014	1.05	8.71	42.75	31.26	16.23	100.00
2019	0.91	21.90	49.56	21.10	6.49	100.00
2024	0.19	5.27	46.55	36.10	11.88	100.00

Seasonal and Annual NDVI Trends:

The NDVI analysis of Satara district revealed significant temporal variations over the studied years. Annual trends indicated a general improvement in vegetation health, particularly in the proportion of dense and very dense vegetation, which increased from 26.36% and 7.45% in 1994 to 36.10% and

11.88% in 2024, respectively. Sparse vegetation areas, which peaked at 44.29% in 2004, declined substantially to 5.27% by 2024, reflecting positive changes in vegetation health. Notable dips in vegetation health were observed during years of climatic stress, such as drought periods, which disrupted the NDVI patterns.

Figure 2 Vegetation health area percentage of Satara District (Maharashtra).

Spatial Distribution of Vegetation Health:

The spatial analysis of vegetation health across Satara District reveals distinct patterns. Dense and very dense vegetation categories were predominantly observed in the western hilly regions, benefiting from

higher rainfall and dense forest cover, which contribute to robust vegetation growth. In contrast, the eastern plains consistently exhibited sparse vegetation due to lower precipitation, intensive agricultural practices, and urban expansion. The central

region acted as a transitional zone, with moderate vegetation being widespread, particularly near irrigation networks and along river courses. This underscores the critical role of water availability in sustaining vegetation health and supporting agricultural activities.

The Temporal Analysis of NDVI Trends:

The temporal analysis of NDVI trends from 1994 to 2024 reveals notable changes in vegetation health across Satara District. Between 1994 and 1999, there is a slight improvement in vegetation density, with higher NDVI values expanding in the western and central parts of the district. However, from 1999 to 2004, a noticeable decline is observed, marked by a significant increase in low NDVI areas, likely caused by environmental stressors such as drought

or deforestation. The period from 2004 to 2009 shows some recovery, with moderate NDVI values increasing in central regions, although sparse vegetation persists in the eastern areas. A significant positive shift occurs from 2009 to 2014, with dense vegetation areas expanding, particularly in the western region, which can be attributed to favorable climatic conditions or conservation efforts. From 2014 to 2019, mixed trends emerge, as dense vegetation decreases in the western areas, while moderate vegetation resurges in the central zones, reflecting climatic variability or land-use changes. Finally, by 2024, there is a resurgence of dense vegetation, especially in the western zones, indicating successful ecological interventions or improved rainfall patterns, along with a significant reduction in sparse vegetation areas.

Figure 2 Spatial Variation of NDVI Satara District (Maharashtra).

Impacts of Climatic and Anthropogenic Factors:

Climatic variability, especially rainfall anomalies, was a primary driver of

NDVI fluctuations across the study period. Periods of reduced rainfall, such as drought years, led to an expansion of sparse vegetation and a decline in dense vegetation

areas. Anthropogenic influences, including deforestation, urbanization, and unsustainable farming practices, exacerbated the stress on vegetation health. However, the increasing trends in dense vegetation in later years suggest the positive impacts of afforestation and water management interventions in specific zones.

Implications for Sustainable Management:

The findings emphasize the critical need for implementing sustainable land and vegetation management practices to enhance ecological resilience in Satara District. Key recommendations include afforestation initiatives in degraded regions to restore vegetation, promoting water-efficient irrigation methods to mitigate water stress, and adopting soil conservation techniques to improve agricultural sustainability. Policymakers and stakeholders must prioritize integrated land and water resource management strategies to ensure long-term vegetation health and ecosystem stability in the region, fostering a balance between ecological preservation and socio-economic development.

Conclusion and Future Scope:

The analysis of NDVI trends in Satara district from 1994 to 2024 demonstrates significant temporal and spatial variations in vegetation health. While periods of climatic stress, such as droughts, led to noticeable declines in vegetation density, the overall trend indicates a positive shift, with dense and very dense vegetation areas expanding significantly over the years. Sparse vegetation, which peaked in 2004, has decreased substantially by 2024, reflecting improved ecological conditions and effective management practices. Spatial patterns highlight the influence of regional factors, with the western hilly areas consistently supporting dense vegetation due to favorable rainfall and forest cover, while the eastern

plains experienced persistent challenges due to lower precipitation, urbanization, and intensive agricultural practices. The central region served as a transitional zone, with moderate vegetation reflecting the critical role of water availability and agricultural interventions. These findings underline the importance of integrated land and water management strategies to sustain and enhance vegetation health. Efforts such as afforestation, efficient irrigation practices, and soil conservation have contributed positively in recent years and must be further strengthened. Sustainable management practices, coupled with ecological restoration and resilience-building measures, are essential to ensure long-term vegetation health and socio-economic stability in the district.

References:

1. Fensholt, R., & Proud, S. R. (2012). Evaluation of Earth observation-based global long-term vegetation trends. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 119, 131-147.
2. Huang, S., Tang, L., Hupy, J. P., et al. (2021). A commentary review on the use of normalized difference vegetation index (NDVI) in the era of popular remote sensing. *Journal of Forest Research*, 32, 1–6. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11676-020-01155-1>
3. IMD (Indian Meteorological Department). (2024). Climatic data for Maharashtra.
4. Milanović, M., Micić, T., Lukic, T., Nenadović, S. S., Basarin, B., Filipović, D. J., Tomić, M., Samardžić, I., Srdić, Z., Nikolić, G., Ninković, M. M., Sakulski, D., & Ristanović, B. (2019). Application of Landsat-derived NDVI in monitoring and assessment of vegetation cover changes in Central Serbia. *Carpathian Journal of Earth and*

- Environmental Sciences, 14(1), 119-129.
<https://doi.org/10.26471/cjees/2019/014/064>
5. Pettorelli, N. (2013). The Normalized Difference Vegetation Index. Oxford University Press.
 6. Pettorelli, N., Vik, J. O., Mysterud, A., Gaillard, J.-M., Tucker, C. J., & Stenseth, N. C. (2005). Using the satellite-derived NDVI to assess ecological responses to environmental change. *Trends in Ecology & Evolution*, 20(9), 503–510.
<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.tree.2005.05.011>
 7. Singh, A., & Rao, S. (2018). Remote sensing applications in vegetation monitoring. *Journal of Environmental Studies*, 25(4), 455-470.
 8. Tucker, C. J. (1979). Red and photographic infrared linear combinations for monitoring vegetation. *Remote Sensing of Environment*, 8, 127-150.
[https://doi.org/10.1016/0034-4257\(79\)90013-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0034-4257(79)90013-0)
 9. USGS Earth Explorer. (2024). Landsat data access. Retrieved from <https://earthexplorer.usgs.gov>
 10. Wang, L., Han, X., Fang, S., & Xiao, F. (2024). Comprehensive assessment of NDVI products derived from Fengyun satellites across China. *Remote Sensing*, 16(8), 1363.
<https://doi.org/10.3390/rs16081363>